

MEDICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THERAPEUTIC EFFECT OF PLASMOLIFTING ON THE ANKLE AND OTHER EXTREMITIES JOINTS

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Abstract

The case of joints of the upper and lower appendages is the matter for discussion of differences in mechanisms of therapeutic effect of the plasmolifting (PL). It involves 3-5 time injections of platelet mass extracted from autologous blood into injury area spaced a week apart. The ankle joint subjected to PL therapy, compared against knee, elbow and shoulder joints, shows an extremely low ability for restoration of its functionality. Therapeutic benefit is contributed by ability of biologically active substances (BAS) and cytokines released by platelets (PI) for activation of metabolic processes within damaged tissues. In turn, it insures restoration of morphofunctional disorders of inflammatory genesis and reparative capabilities.

Successive application of PL is directly dependent on the tissues that make up a certain joint. The positive effect of the introduction of PI auto-suspension is determined by the presence of cytokine donor cells, especially platelet activation factor (PAF). Their sufficient amount triggers PI granulation. An extensive capillary network results with a saturated blood supply and ensures access of granulocyte cells to the sanitized tissue. Besides, basophils and mast cells of connective tissue together with the endothelium of the above capillaries are also PAF sources. All of the above provides a positive therapeutic effect of the PL method on the knee, elbow and shoulder joints unlike the absence of its practical therapeutic effect on the ankle joint and Achilles tendon.

Keywords: plasmolifting, platelets, knee joint, elbow joint, ankle joint.

Introduction. The modern traumatology widely applies stimulating method of regeneration processes of damaged tissues at various musculoskeletal injuries. It ensures the restoration of the morphological integrity of the joints. The therapeutic effect is achieved by introduction into the injured area of either autologous blood, or autologous platelet mass extracted from it. The latter method represents the plasmolifting method (PL) [1]. This kind of approach to the regeneration and treatment with respect to inflammatory processes bases on the ability of cytokines secreted by platelets (PI) to influence the metabolism of damaged tissues. It stimulates the restoration of their structural integrity. However, practical application of the method shows significant variety in achievement of a positive therapeutic effect

with respect to various joints of both the upper and lower extremities [2, 3]. Upon investigation of PL influence on the joints it is important to point out that restoration of damaged tissues includes proliferation, migration of mesenchymal (osteogenic) cells and an increase in morphogenetic proteins, stimulation of angiogenesis and differentiation of new cells, as well as activation of collagen synthesis and osteogenesis [1,4]. Initiation of above processes involves neutrophils, monocytes, macrophages, eosinophils, which release a whole spectrum of cytokines, including the platelet activation factor (PAF). In addition, PIs are able for self-secretion of PAFs, thereby supporting own degranulation. The success of PL is also dependent on the func-

tional sufficiency of the blood supply system. The capillary network of the tissues under sanitation provides quick supply of leukocytes - PAF donors to them, and contains endothelial cells and mast cells (MC), which are also involved in therapeutic process by release of number of factors [5]. At therapy of the musculoskeletal system a complex processes of interaction of cytokines with tissues ensure protection and restoration of joints. It results in reparative and anti-inflammatory effect of PL, restoration of joints, ligaments and tendons [6]. This process includes increased formation of fibroblasts and connective tissue cells, stimulates formation of collagen, hyaluronic acid and elastin. It is followed by increase of migration of osteogenic cells and formation of osteous tissue, improvement in microcirculation and cellular metabolism, tissue respiration, normalization of metabolic processes and activation of local immunity contributed by the growth of new blood vessels [7].

According to Di Matteo B. et al. the tissues of the knee joint show the positive dynamics of recovery processes after plasmolifting. In contrast, the ankle joint and especially the Achilles tendon do not show such success. The authors have found no differences between platelet injection and control injection of saline [2]. Reviewed by Filardo G. et al. it also confirms the difference in recover ability under injection of autothrombocyte mass in the ankle joint (Achilles tendon) on one side and the knee (patellar tendon) and elbow (its lateral tendon) joints on the other one [3]. The difference is determined by the morphology of the tissues composing the formations under sanitation. Obviously, the reasons for such a heterogeneity of the therapeutic effects of PL include, as per above, the presence or absence of a developed blood supply system, which ensures the supply of neutrophils to the joint tissues, as well as the quantity of MC. The knee joint is composed of cartilage and synovium with branched capillaries [8]. It ensures sufficient supply of granulocytes into the tissue under sanitation. Besides, the endothelium of blood vessels is saturated with MC [9]. All of the above PAF donors are able for prevision of abundant degranulation of PL, what is the key aspect for the successful PL therapeutic effect on the knee, elbow and shoulder joints. However capillary network of tissues of the ankle joint and the Achilles tendon is much less extensive. It results with scarcer blood supply [10]. It follows with difficulties for the access of granulocytes to sanitized tissues which, in turn, have fewer amounts of both endothelial cells and MCs observed. Bibliography data [2] correlate with our results of treatment of the ankle joint and the Achilles tendon. It is obvious that insufficient saturation of this joint with the above tissues is the reason for the less sound positive effect of the PL method.

Objective: To reveal the differences in the mechanisms that determine the effectiveness of the plasmolifting method in the treatment of diseases of the ankle joint and the Achilles tendon compared against other joints of the upper and lower appendages.

Materials and methods for research. The work shows the results of long-term studies to identify the success of the PL method in the treatment of various joints of the upper and lower extremities in diverse

groups of patients, of both sexes and different ages. The research was held in Republican Clinical Hospital of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Tatarstan.

The analysis of response to treatment of 2 and 3 stage osteoarthritis bases on research in group of 28 patients (18 male, 10 female) aged from 60 to 80 years old [11]. The analysis of response to treatment of lateral epicondylitis of the elbow joint bases on research in group of 25 patients (16 male, 9 female) aged from 60 to 80 years old [12]. A woman at the age of 56 with a diagnosis of deforming arthrosis of 2nd stage of the right shoulder joint with severe pain syndrome and significant limitation of movements has shown successful response to treatment [13]. Ankle osteoarthritis therapy was held on 7 patients (5 male, 2 female), aged from 50 up to 70 years old.

Autologous plasma course included from 3 up to 5 (on a weekly basis) injections of platelet mass extracted from autologous blood. For gonarthrosis therapy, the injection was carried out into knee cavity, for epicondylitis - in the area of the lateral epicondyle of the humerus. As for the shoulder joint it was made directly into the joint cavity. In the treatment of osteoarthritis of the ankle joint, the injection was carried out into the joint cavity. All patients had severe pain symptoms with daily moderate physical activity. Assessment of knee therapy response performed under WOMAC scale with interval of 1 week, 3 and 6 months after the course. The WOMAC scale (Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index) is a generally accepted questionnaire for assessment of gonarthrosis symptoms. It includes 24 questions divided into three sections. The first subscale (5 questions) is for pain measurement; the second (2 questions) - for stiffness; the third (17 questions) determines physical activity and limitations of knee joint mobility [14]. Before prescription of PL course, over the past years, all patients had received various types of multiple conservative therapy (non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), physiotherapy, analgesic therapy), which has not shown a practical positive effect, or demonstrating short-term improvement. All patients were subjected to a course of autologous plasma therapy comprising 4 injections into the knee joint on a weekly basis. [14].

Effectiveness of the treatment of ankle osteoarthritis on expiration of 1, 2 and 6 months after the course was assessed as per visual analog scale (VAS) of pain, according to which 2 points corresponds to mild pain, from 2 to 4 points - moderate, from 4 to 6 points - severe pain, from 6 to 8 points - maximum and up to 10 points - unbearable pain. [12].

The effectiveness of the treatment of lateral epicondylitis of the elbow joint on expiration of 1, 2, 6 and 12 months after the course was also assessed using the visual analogue pain scale (VAS) [12].

In the case of treatment of osteoarthritis of the shoulder joint, the quality of therapy was assessed by the pain score under the visual analogue scale of pain (VAS). It should be noted that the effectiveness was assessed by comparison against the previous conservative treatment methods (massage, exercise therapy, physiotherapy), which had a slight short-term positive effect.

Before the appointment of the course of PL, the treatment has been carried out for several years. The occurrence of pain was not associated with joint injury (data were not previously published in the scientific literature). Over time, there was a limitation of movement in the right shoulder joint, difficulty in abduction and flexion, which were followed by pain.

Statistical analysis of results was carried with Microsoft Excel 2010 software package and integral Attestat data analysis package [15].

Median values of the score (Me) as well as their discrepancy assessment was held under the nonparametric median criterion. Differences in median values were taken as statistically significant, provided that $p < 0.05$ (the probability that medians belong to samples from different general populations is more than 95%).

Results and their discussion. For all cases, before treatment PL treatment initiation the duration of the disease (arthrosis) of all the joints above varied from 6

months up to 3 years. As it was previously noted, before reference, all patients repeatedly received various types of conservative treatment: NSAIDs, glucocorticoids (GCs), or various types of physiotherapy that have not resulted in any positive effect, or gained just a short-term improvement. In the case of the treatment of osteoarthritis of the knee joint, the median value under WOMAC scale was 74 points before the course. Based on the results of treatment, the patients were divided into 2 groups. In a week most of patients (83%) (first group) have shown decrease down 17 - 27 points, and 17% (second group) – down to 37 - 43 points. After 3 months the value went down to 20 points. After 6 months, pain arose only after long-time household works and going downstairs after extended walk (2 hours and more). Presentation of restoration dynamics for functional capabilities of the joint includes both groups, since it does not interfere with general positive trend of the remission (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Scoring of the results of knee joint treatment. Median values with significant statistic deviation are highlighted in red ($p < 0.05$)

Before the initiation of therapy for lateral epicondylitis of the elbow joint, VAS median value reached 6-7 points when pain interferes with basic needs. The results of treatment within 6 months period were

tracked for 20 patients, within 12 months - for 9 patients. During the first month after the course, pain activity ranged from 1 to 3, after 2 and 6 months - from 0 to 2 points and disappeared after 12 months (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Pain score under VAS scale for patients under elbow joint therapy. Median values with significant statistical deviation are highlighted in red ($p < 0.05$)

Only 1 patient demonstrated an increase in pain up to 4 points within the last period. He has undergone PL retreatment which resulted in 1 point value under VAS scale within 2nd month.

Before the treatment of ankle osteoarthritis, the VAS median value was 4-5 points. By the end of the

first month after treatment initiation, VAS indicator slightly decreased down to 2-3 points. However, the pain syndrome quickly restored with the course of time (in 2 months or later) (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Pain score under VAS scale for patients under ankle joint therapy. Median values with significant statistical deviation are highlighted in red ($p < 0.05$)

The therapy of shoulder joint osteoarthritis by PL method has also demonstrated positive results based on clinical case. Right after the treatment movements of the right joint were significantly limited by severe pain (abduction up to 70, flexion up to 90 degrees), then after 2 years the joint range reached up to 170 for abduction and up to 160 degrees for flexion.

Thus, the PL method is an effective and applicable for treatment injuries of various natures of the joints of the upper and lower extremities at the base of Republican Clinical Hospital of Ministry of Health Care of the Republic of Tatarstan. It is preferable compared against GCs and NSAIDs treatments, since it does not require extended intervals (up to 1 month) between injections, which forces the patient to endure pain, and, moreover,

in some cases does not lead to a positive result. However, the PL method on various joints shows diversity in effectiveness. Whereas the treatment of the knee, elbow and shoulder joints shows a sound positive dynamics, then the therapy of the ankle joint under similar conditions does not demonstrate any significant success. Summing up the positive effect of the PL method on the functional state of the joints of the upper and lower extremities, the following can be noted. In our study, knee joint therapy reduces symptoms by more than 70% of the initial pain intensity within first three months and by almost 60% by the sixth month after the injection course. Even at the absence of significant improvements immediately after the course of treatment,

the maximum effect had been also achieved by the 3rd month after treatment.

For patients with lateral epicondylitis, who had daily moderate physical activity, treatment with the PL method reduces pain symptoms by 80% within the first two months. The maximum effect was gained by the 2nd month, which prolonged for periods of 6 and 12 months. Thus, PL therapy is an effective and safe method of treatment that provides a long-term positive effect for the joints under discussion. In contrast, the treatment of the ankle joint with the introduction of autologous platelet mass shows only a short-term positive effect.

Conclusions. Differences in the therapeutic effects of intra-articular injection of a suspension of autologous blood thrombocytes into the knee and joints of the upper extremities in comparison with the ankle joint are determined by the morphology of their constituent tissues. As for the first three articular formations, branched capillary network, which makes these joints accessible to cells of the granulocytic series, contributes to positive effect. In addition, the capillary endothelium, together with the MCs and basophils contained in it, are sources of PAF. In turn, it triggers the activation of platelets introduced into the joint. All of the above explains the therapeutic effect of PL on the tissues of the knee, elbow and shoulder joints. The previous experience in the treatment of our patients also demonstrates advantages of the injection of autologous platelet mass compared against traditional methods, such as NSAIDs and GCs. In contrast, the insufficiency of the capillary network of the tissues of the ankle joint and the Achilles tendon, and, as a consequence, poor access to them for donor PAF cells, reduces the success of the PL application.

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